

DEVELOPMENT AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF THE DEEP LEARNING MODEL FOR CLASSIFYING BANANA PEST AND DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on developing and evaluating a deep learning model to classify banana pests and diseases. By implementing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and integrating computer vision techniques, the model aims to accurately identify and classify banana pests and diseases. The dataset includes 11 classes of banana health status, each with 1000 images sourced from different repositories, supplemented by manually captured images of banana plants. After preprocessing and augmentation, the model was trained over 20 epochs. Evaluation metrics, including the confusion matrix, recall, precision, overall accuracy, ROC curve, and ROC AUC score, indicated high performance with a precision and recall of 0.91, and an overall accuracy of 0.91. The model effectively distinguished between diseased and healthy plants with minimal misclassification, as confirmed by the robust ROC curve and ROC AUC score of 0.91. These results demonstrate the model's reliability and efficiency in pest and disease classification, providing a valuable tool for timely interventions and improved agricultural productivity in different region. Regular updates with new pest and disease data and advanced algorithms are recommended to further enhance the model's accuracy and efficacy, which will be deployed to a system to be accessible to local farmers.

Keywords: *Machine Learning, Image Processing, Computer Vision, Agriculture*

INTRODUCTION

Food security has become a top priority in the Philippine agricultural sector. Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2: End hunger, food security attainment and greater nutrition, and inspire sustainable farming targets an important human need—access to nourishing, healthy food—as well as the means for ensuring its long-term availability for all. Combating hunger cannot be achieved only through increased food production. Well-effective markets, greater earnings for small farmers, balance access to land and technology, and more investments all help contribute to a robust and productive agricultural sector that promotes food security.

One of the most valuable agricultural products in the Philippines is the banana (Voora et al, 2020). In 2020, the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) listed it as one of the top five crop commodities, alongside other key crops such as rice, corn, coconut, and mango. The country's tropical climate and rich soil conditions make it an ideal environment for banana cultivation (Salvacion,2020), particularly for varieties like Cavendish, Lakatan, and Saba (Gueco et al, 2020). Bananas are not only a staple food for many Filipinos but also a significant export commodity, contributing substantially to the agricultural economy. A variety of factors are affecting the country's banana production. One of the general strategies mentioned in the Philippine Banana Industry Roadmap (2021-2025) by the (BAR) Bureau of Agricultural Research - (DA) Department of Agriculture and the (PCAF) Philippine Council for Agriculture and Fisheries (2022), is the focus on pest and disease management essential for enhancing the productivity and competitiveness of the industry. Small-scale farms and large farms are affected by frequent banana pests and diseases resulting decrease of banana production.

The reduced production of banana can be ascribed to various factors. Since other variety such as Lakatan is very sensitive to the (BBTV) Banana Bunchy Top Virus, the prevalent usage of Lakatan marks improves to the disease's pressure, increasing the chance of incidences and eventually reducing the number of productive plants and delivering low yields per unit area. Moreover, the presence of leaf diseases such as Sigatoka, coupled with soil-borne pests like burrowing nematodes and uncontrolled weed growth, is another crucial factor. If not managed effectively, these issues can lead to a gradual decline in yields over time. Furthermore, according to the Philippine Banana Industry Roadmap (2021–2025), black sigatoka, (BBrMv) banana bract mosaic virus, (BBTV) banana bunchy top virus, bacterial wilt (bugtok and moko), Fusarium wilt (Foc Race 1 and Foc TR4), and banana bunchy top virus (BBTV) are some of the most prevalent and economically significant banana diseases. The current methods of disease diagnosis often involve visual inspections by agricultural experts, a process prone to subjectivity and limitations in scale. Diseases that are manually identified and classified, takes a lot of time, and requires the expertise of specialists.

The advancements in agricultural technology, particularly in the domain of banana plant disease classification (Krishnan et al, 2022) and management, reflect a growing reliance on machine learning and deep learning methodologies (Singh and Athisayamani,2020). Various studies have explored innovative approaches, but they also exhibit some gaps

that warrant further investigation. For instance, Selvaraj et al (2020) used remote sensing and machine learning to detect diseases, illustrating the power of integrating advanced sensor technologies with data-driven models. However, the accuracy of their models may be limited by the resolution and scope of the remote sensing data, potentially overlooking smaller but significant disease symptoms. This highlights the need for finer-grained detection methods in practical applications. Building on this, Narayanan et al (2022) employed a convolutional neural network (CNN) to classify banana diseases, emphasizing the effectiveness of deep learning (Sangeetha et al, 2023) and image processing (Aruraj et al, 2019). But one significant limitation was the small size of datasets. Developing a model with broader disease classification capabilities is needed to ensure adaptability across various disease types and environmental conditions.

In contrast, the incorporation of deep learning algorithms and computer vision offers a promising solution to automate and improve the accuracy of disease detection (Liu et al, 2022). This research focuses on utilizing deep learning algorithms with computer vision techniques to create an innovative Banana Disease Classification. By using advanced technologies, this study purposes to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of disease diagnosis, providing timely and targeted interventions for farmers. The adoption and execution of these outlined strategies are anticipated to achieve industry goals and objectives, foster inclusive growth in terms of competitiveness, sustainability, and promote the overall development of the banana industry.

This study employs (CNN) Convolutional Neural Networks for the classification of banana pests and diseases. The researchers used large number of datasets and more classes to make it useful into the large agricultural areas. This study also integrates computer vision techniques to analyze and interpret images and provide the classified status of the plant. For the evaluation of the performance of the model the research uses statistical evaluation such as Confusion Matrix, Precision, Recall, Overall Accuracy, ROC Curve, and ROC AUC Score.

Research Questions

1. How is machine learning used to improve the accuracy and efficiency of banana pest and disease classification compared to traditional diagnostic methods?
2. How are computer vision techniques applied to effectively analyze images for the classification of banana diseases and pests?
3. How can the accuracy of the CNN model be improved for classifying banana pests and diseases, considering factors such as dataset quality, size, and augmentation techniques?
4. How well does the CNN model perform across various evaluation metrics such as precision, recall, and overall accuracy in detecting and classifying different types of banana pests and diseases?

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researchers were employed a developmental research approach, resulting in final products that undergo evaluation.

Datasets

The datasets were collected in different dataset repositories separated into different disease classes. To make the study more useful, the researchers added the healthy dataset by manually capturing a healthy banana plant. Finally, the study used eleven classes of banana health status with 1000 images for each class. Figure 2 shows the sample image for each class.

Figure 1. Dataset

Data Preprocessing and Augmentation

All gathered images were classified into identified banana diseases. The format of each image is .jpg. Augmentation is used to balance the dataset and to expand the volume of dataset. The datasets collected from different repositories were already increase up to 1000 images per class using data augmentation. Since the datasets were already augmented, the researchers used a limited way of augmentation to avoid overfitting. The datasets are split into a train set, which comprises 80% images, 10% for validation, and

a test set which comprises the remaining 10%. The images were resized into 128 x 128 resolution to fit the input layer of Deep Learning Model.

Training and Evaluation of the Model

After the data preprocessing and augmentation, the researchers used CNN to develop the model. The researchers set 20 epochs for the training of the model for classifying the banana illness.

Evaluation Metrics

These are the following criteria that are used in evaluating deep learning model. The following statistical validation tools are used by the researchers to determine the overall applicability of the trained model.

A. Confusion Matrix

This matrix matches the target values with the predictions made by the machine learning model, giving a full view of the classification model's performance and errors it is making.

B. Precision

This statistical validation indicates the number of correctly predicted cases that are positive.

$$\text{Precision} = \text{TP} / \text{TP} + \text{FP}$$

C. Recall

Recall indicates the ratio of actual positive instances that the trained model predicts correctly.

$$\text{Recall} = \text{TP} / \text{TP} + \text{FN}$$

D. F1 Score

The F1-score is the mean of recall and precision that provides a combination of two metrics.

$$\text{F1-score} = 2 / (1 / \text{Recall} + 1 / \text{Precision})$$

E. Accuracy

Accuracy is the calculation percentage of correct predicted value out of the total predicted value for the testing data. It is computed by getting the value of the number of correct predicted value divided by the total value of predictions.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \text{TP} + \text{TN} / \text{TP} + \text{FP} + \text{TN} + \text{FN}$$

F. ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic)

The ROC curve is a graphical record that shows the performance of the model among all classification bases. This plots two parameters: Recall or the True Positive Rate (TPR), and the FPR or the False Positive Rate.

G. AUC (Area Under the ROC Curve)

The AUC-ROC measures the entire 2D area under the ROC which provides a comprehensive performance across all possible classification bases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Through the utilization of Machine Learning and computer vision technologies, the developed model demonstrated promising results in accurately identifying and classifying banana illnesses. The evaluation metrics indicated high precision, recall, and overall accuracy, as well as a robust performance reflected in the ROC Curve and ROC AUC Score.

The developed Banana Disease Classification Model underwent rigorous evaluation using various metrics to assess its performance in accurately identifying and classifying banana illnesses in the region.

Confusion Matrix Analysis:

The Confusion Matrix shows the detailed summary of the classification results, make a distinction between (TP) true positives, (FP) false positives, (TN) true negatives and (FN) false negatives. In our model, we observed a high value of TP and TN, indicating that the model effectively identified both diseased and healthy banana plants. However, there were relatively few false positives and false negatives, suggesting a minor tendency for misclassification. Overall, the model demonstrated robust performance.

Figure 2. Confusion Matrix

Precision and Recall:

With a precision of 0.91 and a recall of 0.91, our system exhibited high accuracy in identifying diseased banana plants while minimizing false positives and false negatives. These metrics reflect the system's ability to precisely classify banana illnesses, essential for effective disease management strategies.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
bacterial_soft_rot	0.84	0.90	0.87	109
banana_aphids	0.95	0.98	0.96	42
banana_insect_pest	0.89	0.89	0.89	61
banana_moko_disease	0.81	0.87	0.84	39
black_sigatoka	0.90	0.92	0.91	95
bract_mosaic_virus	0.93	0.77	0.84	35
fruit_scarring_beetle	0.88	1.00	0.94	15
healthy_leaf	0.90	0.93	0.92	75
panama_disease	0.93	0.90	0.92	42
pseudostem_weevil	0.96	0.94	0.95	275
yellow_sigatoka	0.97	0.81	0.89	43
accuracy			0.91	831
macro avg	0.91	0.90	0.90	831
weighted avg	0.91	0.91	0.91	831

Figure 3. Precision, Recall, & F1-Score

Overall Accuracy:

The system's overall accuracy, determined by the percentage of classified instances correctly to the total instances evaluated, was measured at 0.91. This shows that the model achieved a high level of accuracy in classifying both diseased and healthy banana plants, contributing to reliable disease diagnosis and intervention decisions for farmers in the region.

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Accuracy for each class:
[0.84482759 0.95348837 0.8852459 0.80952381 0.89690722 0.93103448
0.88235294 0.8974359 0.92682927 0.95571956 0.97222222]

Average accuracy: 0.91
Overall accuracy: 0.91
Score: 0.91

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Figure 4. Overall Accuracy

ROC Curve:

Our system exhibited a well-defined ROC curve, and the calculated ROC AUC Score of 0.91 confirms its excellent discriminatory power, further validating its efficacy in disease classification.

Figure 5. ROC Curve

Conclusions

The results of the evaluation metrics demonstrate the effectiveness and robust performance of the developed Banana Disease Classification Model in accurately identifying and classifying banana pests and illnesses. The high precision, recall, and overall accuracy, coupled with a strong ROC Curve and ROC AUC Score, affirm the reliability and efficiency of the system in disease diagnosis. By integration of CNN and computer vision technologies, the system offers a promising solution to automate and enhance the accuracy of disease detection, providing timely interventions for farmers to mitigate crop losses and improve agricultural productivity.

Recommendations

Regular updates incorporating new disease data and expanded algorithms can further improve the system's accuracy and efficacy in disease diagnosis. The developed model will be deployed within a system to be accessible to farmers in the region.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adheres to ethical standards and guidelines for conducting research involving image data and machine learning models. The images used for training and testing the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) were obtained from publicly available datasets or through ethical means, ensuring that no harm was caused to individuals or the environment during data collection. The research did not involve human subjects, personal data, or sensitive information, eliminating the need for personal consent. All data sources used in this research were properly cited and acknowledged, and the research process followed the principles of transparency, fairness, and integrity.

Furthermore, this research complies with the ethical guidelines of relevant institutions and authorities. Any potential biases in the machine learning model were carefully monitored and mitigated to avoid unfair discrimination in the classification of pests and diseases. The findings of this study are intended solely for academic and agricultural development purposes, with the goal of contributing to better crop management practices. The study respects the privacy of data sources and ensures that the outcomes are disseminated responsibly and accurately.

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